

The Influence and Interaction between Bhakti Movement and Sufism

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Abstract:- one most significant aspect of religion is the the dimension of human spirituality. mystical experience aur human security is not The Legacy of any particular religion. on the contrary, it is common to all religions..It is not only the common element but also the for essence of every religion. consequently, all religions have undertaken studies of their respective mystical Experience At The intellectual or scholarly plane. these theoretical or doctorinal studies as well as practices constitute the wrap and Wolf Of w is known as mysticism. now different religions have their different versions or formulations mysticism. the mysticism of one religion differs from that of another religion in many respects. in addition, even within the same religion there may be different saves aur approaches to mysticism. in this paper an attempt is made to study the the mystical dimensionHuman being at the inter cultural plane and perennial quest for peace full coexistence; firstly with reference to Indian tradition Bhakti and then in the light of the Islamic spiritual tradition or say sufism . finally. e whistle also discuss the influence and interaction between the Bhakti movement and sufism highlighting the significant role of spiritual dimension of Islam and Hinduism and their religious and literary Trends and legacies for encouraging. creating and promoting suitable atmosphere for mutual understanding and suitable peaceful coexistence on the Indian mystical soil.

I. INTRODUCTION

Generally in the history of humankind religion had been playing a vital throughout the centuries. it became a beacon of light and turning point in the life of man. Religious life, viz, emotional responses, believes, devotional practices etc. religion has got to have a corresponding value system and way of life. it differs from both science and philosophy in emphasizing Engagement involvement and commitment. the philosophy of religion studies the concept and belief system of religion as well as the perennial phenomena and religious experience and emotional and contemplative practices on which these belief systems rest and out of which they have emerge add in the long drawn out historical evaluation ¹

Devotion property is Essential elements of any religion. it plays a vital role thistic religion. Bhakt is deeply rooted in hindu dharm Moksh, the highest goal in Hindu religious value system, can be attained through yoga. yoga easy unique synthesis of the three way:1- the Jnana Marga2: Karma Marg3: Bhakti Marg. however, it is generally assumed that

the bhakti Mar Gaya is the best way to achieve salvation and includes the other ways as well.

Sufism aur sufi movement: sufism is as old as Islam itself. It is generally known to be the spiritual or inner dimension of Islam. the outer or exotersic dimension may be regarded as a religious worldview. however both inner and Outer or esoteric and exoteric aspects of religion are important aspects of Islam. they are, in reality, the two sides of the same coin. as a matter of historical fact The Spiritual dimension of Islam has been overremphasized 48 is it Deemed to be representing the true spirit of religion.

The outstanding feature of the work is that it also gives an intensive account of the Islamic spirituality long before the emergence of sufism²

➤ *Main common themes between Sufism and Bhakti movement:*

In order to understand the CP to peaceful coexistence of interaction between the two separate scores of the two great religion Hinduism and Islam- it seems appropriate to select some common themes of interaction with reference to mediaeval India. however, it would be in order to point out the general catholicity Outlook demonstrated buy flowers of Islam. Islamic civilizations and culture had been truly Universal in the sense that it at once incorporated elements from the existing civilizations and religious and in its turn inspired and influenced many of them. Islamic worldview and value system left its remarkable impact in different aspects of human life, more aspecially mens ritual moorings. the Early development of Islamic spiritual tradition after Imam Ali took place in what were the centres of early christianity namely Egypt Syria and Iraq. Latest outline the main themes of interaction and mutual consent between the two schools of spiritual tradition Bhakti movement and sufism.

- *Conception of God:*

Both Bhakti movement and sufism strongly believe in theunitarian conception of God. the ultimate reality is one as mentioned in the vedas, Upanishad and the Bhagavad Gita. according to the Vedas the one rial is worshipped in various capacities.

- *Love of God:*

Another outstanding theme of interaction and sincere common Endeavour of goodwill between Bhakti jump in sufism is love of God the foundation of any spiritual system. m in Bhakti movement and sufism love of god is a deemed to

be one of the important practices leading to apprehension cognition and realization of God.

Kabir is a genius a different order. He has gazed into the mystery of life.....of india and apstle of the faith of humanity who taught that the divine disclosed itself in the human race as a whole.³

- *Service to humanity:*

Besides unity of God and love of God, the third important is also among the main theme of interaction between the Bhakti movement and sufism love and service to humanity. in this regard the representatives of both the mystical tradition believe family that love and service to humanity. is, in real sense, the love and Service to God, in this way, these mystics cut of the roots of the the discrimination against human being on the basis of caste, creed and colour. they made good actions, just behaviour and human service the criteria for Supriya t and greatness. Kabir himself for experienced various critical stages in his life, he passed through all tenses with the sufis and bugs described such as contrition and sorrow hope and fear intimacy in contemplating his beauty and awe it is Majesty separation and union absence and presence.⁴

All these States helped Kabeer to love and work for human beings in order to please his good. through the service and love two ruminative one May obtain one spiritual mission, A distinguished line of sufis includes Amir Khusro, Aladdin, Iraqi, Bu Ali qalandar, Jamal Aladdin Hamid Aladin Nagori and others⁵

- *Role of Persian language in Indo Islamic Mystic tradition:*

In fact the entire phenomenon of religious diversity is one of the crucial questions with which the present religious discourage is fishing Muslim think up most recently have tried to deal with the issue of according to to their intellectual trainings and tension as well as to their emerging situations. however, the right and perfect for complete answer is yet to be required for which we all or also striving, so we'll discussing the two important spiritual traditions but the jump and sufis are of the great religion Hinduism and Islam we are hopeful to find the more common Grounds of mutual understanding goodwill and peaceful coexistence as examined and practiced by these great mystical moment and with the Persian language and literature

II. CONCLUSION

Contemporary India is deeply impacted by factor moment, sufism and Persian literature. the value of freedom equality Brotherhood goodness kindness love and Corporation incorporated into beach streams of scholarship and frameworks for yumen Fellowship are the guiding values of modern Indian society and polity. constitute The controlling vision of modern India. . the long drawn out roll off bhagt sufis and Indu Pareshan V is an achievement of great significance in the Cultural synthesis of India. it is time we take up a great significance in the cultural synthesis of India. Beach moments historical analysis with a view to

anchor A Beacon light for our future generation to love and live in the atmosphere of mutual understanding goodwill and peaceful coexistence.

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